

FEATURES OF STUDYING LYRICAL WORK AT SCHOOL

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ANNOTATION

Lyrics are a special kind of literature that has its own characteristics and properties and they must be taken into account when studying in literature lessons.

Poetry is born from a sense of the world as boundlessness and harmony. Tyutchev's line: "Everything is in me, and I am in everything" conveys a mentality that makes possible the openness of a lyrical monologue and the audacity of a poetic metaphor. Only poetry is given the ability to connect "distant concepts" (Pushkin).

Poetry is endowed with enormous power of generality. Each reader must recite a poem on his own behalf. The uniqueness of the poet's intonation in the lyrics becomes the property of everyone. Finally, a lyric poem is a fusion of the moment and eternity. This is the moment of the present, in which it flows as a movement of feelings, and the whole essence of a person, the history of his relationship with the world. In a lyric poem, short as lightning, the reader should be able to discern the whole world, illuminated by this instantaneous

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Children become fans of poetry early. The freedom of children's associations and the attitude towards the world as a discovery, a miracle, connects preschoolers with poetry and encourages them to repeat poems spellbound, like a song. The need for poetry comes later, at the border of adolescence and youth, when a growing person feels the uniqueness of his personality, when the environment is perceived with excitement and intensity. However, the language of poetry becomes native to schoolchildren with certain efforts from family and teachers. We cannot boast that reading poetry is a tradition in every family. Therefore, many literature teachers begin the lesson with a five-minute poetry lesson, when students take turns presenting their favorite poems to the class. [3. p. 12-14]

Being well-read in poetry is one of the main conditions for becoming familiar with poetry. Students with a low level of literary development, even with the correct emotional reactions, cannot translate them into conceptual

terms. In developed students, when perceiving lyrics, the sharpness of their personal relationship to the work is especially noticeable. For average students, purely logical mastery of a poem turns out to be a sign not of victory, but rather of defeat, since there is a lyrical contact between the reader and the poet. The work of imagination and especially the awareness of artistic form are, as a rule, the most backward elements of perception when reading lyrics in comparison with other types of literature.

Thus, precisely because the poem requires the reader to join the lyrical hero of the poem, to emotionally enter into the situation of the work, special difficulties are created when reading and analyzing. The student reader either does not respond to the problem and situation of the poem, or replaces them with his own life experience. “Non-connection” and “switching” are extremes of perception that must be overcome in school analysis, so that a personal association certainly arises when reading, but does not obscure the poetic content and structure of the verse. [2. p. 20-21]

Often, when reading and analyzing, a poem breaks up into separate lines, words that do not merge into a powerful, single lyrical flow. To reveal the movement of poetic thought, to discover the “overflow” of feelings, to find the reasons for its variability, to identify and justify the cross-cutting, central images of the poem, to find a justification for the chain of poetic associations - this is one of the most important tasks in the study of lyrics.

The search for the movement of lyrical thought convinces students that a poem is a single world infinite in its possibilities. When studying lyrics, it is necessary to show the poem as a poetic whole, as a dynamic system in which everything is interconnected and interdependent.

A lyric poem is an independent world, but not closed in itself. Comprehension of a poem is possible only against the background of the system of poetic creativity from which it was born. For a full perception of lyrics, it is necessary, especially in high school, to study the poem in the context of the poet's entire work, to discover the connections of an individual poem with the poet's worldview, the originality of his poetic manner.

So, the study of poetry in school is endowed with a number of specific qualities, without which the reader's contact with poetry will not take place:

1. A lyric poem requires especially careful and repeated efforts by the teacher to create a “set” for reading. Reviving personal associations and creating a real background in which the poem was born when reading should help to concretize poetic images in the reader's mind.

2. The first reading of a lyric poem is most useful for the teacher himself, since the strength of the emotional impression depends on the specific address. When read, a lyric poem should give the impression of a monologue born “today, here, now.” And only this immediacy of address can awaken the feelings of the students.

3. The transition from reading to analysis when studying a lyric poem is especially difficult. The students' feelings, alarmed by reading, are afraid of the "algebra" of analysis. Therefore, the acute clash of subjective reader opinions, the comparison of musical and acting interpretations of the text should imperceptibly involve in analysis, which sometimes proceeds in hidden forms.

The authors of many modern programs consider it possible and even necessary to use the same principles, methods and methods in teaching literature as in teaching natural sciences. In particular; it is considered appropriate to use such a scientific research function; as an explanation. In our opinion, the task of school literature teaching is not to explain a work of art, but to help the student understand it. It is the desire to explain that leads to the fact that a work of art becomes an object of study. [1. p. 44-47]

The inadmissibility of transferring the methods of natural sciences to the field of humanities is obvious to many scientists today. However, modern literary education programs (T.G. Avlova, M.B. Ladygin.) turn to the methods of natural sciences and use theoretical knowledge as the main component that ensures the student's literary development.

Another danger lurks in the formula “literature is a textbook of life,” which T.F. traditionally relies on. Kurdyumov and which leads to the “expansion of life into art” (B.A. Uspensky), to the destruction of the integrity of a work of art. In the program edited by V.G. Marantzman, which we primarily focused on in our work, a work of art acquires the role that an aesthetic phenomenon should have in the process of a student's literary development, and the main condition for this development is the formation and improvement of the student's reading skills. Taking into account the age characteristics of schoolchildren, the program offers a system of growth and gradual complication of the reader's aesthetic activity. The study of a work of art and theoretical and literary concepts, the students' own literary creativity is a single process, the central event of which is the personal understanding of the literary text.

This is achieved by an interesting system of complementary tasks: from reading a work of art to its analysis, the basis of which is the interpretive moment and the dialogical nature of the relationship between both the recipient

and the work, and the recipients, in the role of whom are classmates and the teacher, and then - to one's own creative activity, which can be, to a certain extent, regulated, directed, and given by the entire course and content of the process of studying a work. Creative tasks such as choosing music, a work of art, or independently completing an illustration for a text, suggesting scenery and costumes for a drama, writing a work in the genre studied, etc. d. help to perceive the work as an aesthetic phenomenon, and not a moralized fact of life.

Creativity of A.S. Pushkin is studied in accordance with the principle of gradation, that is, in each class. Works are selected that are accessible to the age of the students, preparing them for the future perception of the poet's work as a multifaceted and complex artistic phenomenon. [4. p. 122-123]

Creativity of A.S. Pushkin is represented at all stages of literary education: in elementary school, at the stage of naive realism (grades 4-6), during the period of egocentrism (middle-level classes) and in high school (grades 10-11). The life and work of the poet are most actively studied in middle-level classes, which can include grades 6-9. The program at this stage of literary education examines the poet's work based on the principle of gradation, when in each class individual works and fragments of the poet's biography are studied, helping to understand them. And only the 9th grade, which is also classified as the middle level (since some students complete their schooling at this time and enter the system of primary and secondary vocational education), studies the topic "A.S. Pushkin" monographically. Therefore, it is in the 9th grade, being the final level of secondary education, that the unity of classroom and extracurricular forms of organizing the educational process is especially important.

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